

UPGRADATION OF LOW-GRADE LIMESTONE BY USING A SUITABLE BENEFICIATION METHOD

A PROJECT REPORT

Submitted by

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ABSTRACT

This report deals with the suitable beneficiation process to be implemented in mineral processing plant for upgradation of low grade limestone. This report briefly lists out the background, objective and industrial applications of the project. The field of mineral processing, need for it and the various steps involved in mineral processing are briefly discussed. This report deals with the various flotation methods used for concentration their advantages and disadvantages and the recovery of mineral from such flotation methods. The mechanism and various structures of cell and column flotation has been discussed in detail. Various pre-concentration methods like Jigging, Dense media separation, Spirals etc., and their suitability with column flotation has been discussed in the later chapter. Finally several sets of flowsheets, formed from the data obtained from various literatures have been included.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Beneficiation can be used to upgrade the ore from Low grade to High grade. In this study, an attempt has been made to create Processing plant Flow sheets by choosing a suitable method of upgradation. In order to achieve this, different combinations of methods has been used for the making of Flow sheets.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF THE PROJECT

Mineral processing also known as ore dressing, is the process to separate commercially valuable mineral from the ores. The industrial application of the ore mainly depends upon the quality of the ore. If the ore is in low quality, it's not a waste. By using various techniques, it can be used as a valuable material.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The main objectives of the project are

- To improve the quality of Limestone by using suitable Beneficiation Technique with minimum Cost
- To prepare a Flowsheet on upgradation of Limestone

1.4 INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS OF THE PROJECT

The Industrial applications of the project are,

- It can be used to improve the economic value of the ore by increasing the grade.
- Even the rejects may contain some valuable minerals, by using the beneficiation, the valuable minerals can be separated

1.5 ORGANISATION OF THESIS

Chapter 1 deals with the introduction to the project and also the objectives, background and industrial applications of the project

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 MINERAL PROCESSING

The first process that most of the ores or minerals undergo after they leave any mine, is mineral processing or mineral/ ore dressing. It is a process of ore preparation, milling, and ore dressing or ore beneficiation. Ore dressing is a process of mechanically separating the grains of ore minerals from the gangue minerals. It is done in order to produce a concentrate containing most of the ore minerals and a tailing part (discard) containing the rest of the gangue minerals. This is an important aspect in Geo exploration and industrial economic geology.

Treatment of ores to get their metallic concentrate into useful products (concentrate) of smaller bulk, and simultaneously to separate the worthless material (gangue) into discardable waste (tailing), is required for materials manufacturing. The treatment process is called as mineral dressing. There are two major primary operations in mineral processing. One is comminution and the other one is concentration. In addition to these, there are many other sequential secondary operations involved in mineral processing including sampling and dewatering. The cleaning of ore by the removal of certain valueless portions are also needed for maintaining the quality in output. The fundamental operations of ore-dressing processes are: a) the breaking apart of the associated constituents of the ore by mechanical methods and b) the separation of the valuable components (beneficiation) into concentrate and tailings, using appropriate methods.

There are two fundamental operation in Mineral processing: namely the release, or liberation, of valuable minerals from their waste gangue materials, and separation of these values from the gangue, this latter process being known as concentration.

Liberation of the valuable minerals from the gangue is accomplished by comminution, which involves crushing, and, if necessary, grinding, to such a particle size that the product is a mixture of relatively clean particles of mineral and gangue. Grinding is often the greatest energy consumer, accounting for up to 50% of a concentrator's energy consumption. As it is this process which achieves liberation of values from gangue, it is also the process which is essential for efficient separation of the minerals, and it is often said to be the key to good mineral processing. In order to produce clean concentrates with little contamination with

gangue minerals, it is necessary to grind the ore finely enough to liberate the associated metals. Fine grinding, however, increases energy costs, and can lead to the production of very fine untreat-able "slime" particles which may be lost into the tailings. Grinding therefore becomes a compromise between clean (high-grade) concentrates, operating costs and losses of fine minerals. If the ore is low grade, and the minerals have very small grain size and are disseminated through the rock, then grinding energy costs and fines losses can be high, unless the nature of the minerals is such that a pronounced difference in some property between the minerals and the gangue is available.

2.2 NECESSITY OF MINERAL PROCESSING

Ore is an aggregate of economically important minerals from which a valuable metallic constituent can be profitably mined and extracted. Most of the rock deposits contain metals or minerals. When the concentration of valuable minerals or metals is too low to justify for mining, it is considered to be a waste or gangue material. Within an ore body, the valuable minerals are surrounded by gangue minerals. It is due to this primary reason, we need to go for mineral processing. It is necessary to liberate and concentrate those valuable minerals from the bulk mass through a suitable mechanical treatment.

2.3 VARIOUS STEPS INVLOVED IN MINERAL PROCESSING

The following are the major processing methods involved in ore dressing/ mineral processing:

1. Size reduction (Crushing, Grinding)
2. Size control (Screening, Classification)
3. Enrichment (Washing, Gravity separation, Flotation, Magnetic separation, Leaching)
4. Upgrading (Sedimentation, Mechanical dewatering, Thermal drying, Thermal processing)
5. Materials handling (Unloading, Storing, Feeding, Conveying)
6. Slurry handling (Slurry transportation, Agitation and mixing)
7. Wear in operation
8. Operation and environment

2.4 FLOWSHEET

The flowsheet shows diagrammatically the sequence of operations in the plant. In its simplest form it can be presented as a block diagram in which all operations of similar character are grouped. In this case comminution deals with all crushing, grinding and initial rejection. The next block, "separation", groups the various treatments incident to production of concentrate and tailing. The third, "product handling", covers the disposal of the products.

Fig. 1 Simple Flowsheet

Fig. 2 Flowsheet Model

2.5 LIBERATION

One of the major objectives of comminution is the liberation, or release, of the valuable minerals from the associated gangue minerals at the coarsest possible particle size. If such an aim is achieved, then not only is energy saved by the reduction of the amount of fines produced, but any subsequent separation stages become easier and cheaper to operate. The particles of "locked" mineral and gangue are known as middlings, and further liberation from this fraction can only be achieved by further comminution. The "degree of liberation" refers to the percentage of the mineral occurring as free particles in the ore in relation to the total content. This can be high if there are weak boundaries between mineral and gangue particles, which is often the case with ores composed mainly of rock-forming minerals, particularly sedimentary minerals.

Fig. 3 Gangue Material

2.5 CONCENTRATION

The object of mineral processing, regardless of the methods used, is always the same, i.e. to separate the minerals into two or more products with the values in the concentrates, the gangue in the tailings, and the "locked" particles in the middlings. Such separations are, of course, never perfect, so that much of the middlings produced are, in fact, misplaced particles, i.e. those particles which ideally should have reported to the concentrate or the tailings. This is often particularly serious when treating ultra-fine particles, where the efficiency of separation is usually low. In such cases, fine liberated valuable mineral particles often report in the middlings and tailings.

CHAPTER 3

FLOTATION

3.1 INTRODUCTION

Flotation is undoubtedly the most important and versatile mineral processing technique, and both its use and application are continually being expanded to treat greater tonnages and to cover new areas.

Flotation is a physico-chemical separation process that utilises the difference in surface properties of the valuable minerals and the unwanted gangue minerals. The theory of froth flotation is complex, involving three phases (solids, water, and froth) with many sub processes and interactions, and is not completely understood.

The process of material being recovered by flotation from the pulp comprises three mechanisms:

- (1) Selective attachment to air bubbles (or "true flotation").
- (2) Entrainment in the water which passes through the froth.
- (3) Physical entrapment between particles in the froth attached to air bubbles (often referred to as "aggregation").

The attachment of valuable minerals to air bubbles is the most important mechanism and represents the majority of particles that are recovered to the concentrate. Although true flotation is the dominant mechanism for the recovery of valuable mineral, the separation efficiency between the valuable mineral and gangue is also dependent on the degree of entrainment and physical entrapment. Unlike true flotation, which is chemically selective to the mineral surface properties, both gangue and valuable minerals alike can be recovered by entrainment and entrapment. Drainage of these minerals occurs in the froth phase and controlling the stability of this phase is important to achieve an adequate separation. In industrial flotation plant practice, entrainment of unwanted gangue can be common and hence a single flotation stage is uncommon. Often several stages of flotation (called "circuits") are required to reach an economically acceptable quality of valuable mineral in the final product.

True flotation utilises the differences in physicochemical surface properties of particles of various minerals. After treatment with reagents, such differences in surface

properties between the minerals within the flotation pulp become apparent and, for flotation to take place, an air bubble must be able to attach itself to a particle, and lift it to the water surface.

The agitator provides enough turbulence in the pulp phase to promote collision of particles and bubbles which results in the attachment of valuable particles to bubbles and their transport into the froth phase for recovery. The process can only be applied to relatively fine particles, because if they are too large the adhesion between the particle and the bubble will be less than the particle weight and the bubble will therefore drop its load.

Fig. 4 Flotation Mechanism

3.2 REVERSE FLOTATION

In flotation concentration, the mineral is usually transferred to the froth, or float fraction, leaving the gangue in the pulp or tailing. This is direct flotation and the opposite is reverse flotation, in which the gangue is separated into the float fraction. So, the silica will be removed in the mineralized froth zone and concentrate ore is collected downside, reverse to the normal flotation.

The function of the froth phase is to enhance the overall selectivity of the flotation process. The froth achieves this by reducing the recovery of entrained material to the concentrate stream, while preferentially retaining the attached material. This increases the concentrate grade whilst limiting as far as possible the reduction in recovery of valuables. The relationship between recovery and grade is a trade-off that needs to be managed according to operational constraints and is incorporated in the management of optimum froth

stability. As the final separation phase in a flotation cell, the froth phase is a crucial determinant of the grade and recovery of the flotation process.

The mineral particles can only attach to the air bubbles if they are to some extent water-repellent, or hydrophobic. Having reached the surface, the air bubbles can only continue to support the mineral particles if they can form a stable froth, otherwise they will burst and drop the mineral particles. To achieve these conditions it is necessary to use the numerous chemical compounds known as flotation reagents.

Most minerals are not water-repellent in their natural state and flotation reagents must be added to the pulp. The most important reagents are the collectors, which adsorb on mineral surfaces, rendering them hydrophobic (or aerophilic) and facilitating bubble attachment. The frothers help maintain a reasonably stable froth. Regulators are used to control the flotation process; these either activate or depress mineral attachment to air bubbles and are also used to control the pH of the system.

Here, in Limestone the silica is containing oxygen, as naturally it is anions. By using cationic collectors, the silica can be removed and Limestone will be separated by Reverse Flotation. But it is applicable to only low level silica removal only. For high level silica removal, other methods can be used.

3.3 COLUMN FLOTATION

Separation of valuable minerals from gangue is far from ideal in conventional mechanical cells. Column flotation, invented in the early sixties, proved to be a better alternative to the conventional cells. The main advantages of column flotation are :

- i) improved recovery,
- ii) higher grade,
- iii) lower capital and operating costs,
- iv) less wear and tear due to absence of moving parts and
- v) requirement of less floorspace

Fig. 5 Column Flotation

From an operational point, two main zones can be identified : i) collection zone, where feed entering 1-2 m below the top of the column flows down counter current to bubbles rising from a gas sparger near the bottom of the column and ii) a cleaning zone, where the froth rising from the collection zone is washed of the entrained gangue by counter current wash water introduced at the top of the column. Finally, the washed froth overflows from the launder and is collected as the product while the tailings are discharged from the bottom. Commercial flotation columns can have either square or round cross-section and are generally upto 15 meters tall.

Since there are no moving parts in the column the main operating variables are the flow rates:

- feed air,
- wash water,
- product and tailings.
- Column dimensions,
- bubble size,
- air holdup and the reagent dosages.

To normalize the effect of flow rates in different sizes of columns, the superficial velocities, defined as the volumetric flow rates per unit area of cross section, are used.

Another variable which is generally mentioned with reference to column operation is the bias rate which is the difference between the tailings rate and the feed rate. If the value is positive it is called positive bias and if it is negative it is called negative bias. Alternatively displacement wash ratio defined as the ratio of quantity of wash water to the quantity of water reporting to the concentrate.

As mentioned earlier, the column can be divided into two distinctively different zones : the collection zone and the recovery zone or the froth zone. Both of these need separate treatment.

COLLECTION ZONE

In the collection zone the main factors affecting the recovery and grade are the bubble size and air hold up besides the flow rates.

Air Holding and Bubble Size

The volume fraction of liquid displaced by air is known as the air holdup, E . The bubble size influences the hold up and the bubble surface available for carrying the values. Except for clay type particles where viscosity effects dominate, in other cases slurry density and viscosity often have approximately equal and opposite effects on bubble rise velocity and therefore on holdup. It has been shown that bubble loading may result in significant increase in holdup, the increase being less significant for finer bubbles.

Effect of Gas and Liquid Rates on Hold up

It can be seen that the air hold up increase approximately linearly in the beginning and then deviates above a certain J_9 . The linear section is characterized by uniform distribution of bubbles, nearly uniform in size, and is known as bubbly flow regime. This is the region of interest in column flotation. Above this air rate, hold up is characterized by large bubbles, rising rapidly displacing water and small bubbles downward. This region is known as the churn turbulent region and the operation will be unsteady in this region. For a given flow rate of air, increase in counter current flow of water increases hold up as a result of relative decrease in bubble rise velocity. However, increase of J , will decrease the maximum J_g for bubbly flow regime.

Addition of frother

Addition of frother up to a certain level has a pronounced effect of reducing bubble size, resulting in reduced bubble rise velocity and consequent increase in hold up.

Mixing in Collection Zone

Laboratory flotation columns typically operate under plug flow conditions while plant columns operate under conditions intermediate to plug flow and perfectly mixed flow. For these columns plug flow dispersion model is shown to provide a good working basis.

Over the bubble size range relevant to column flotation, decrease of bubble size is reported to increase dispersion.

Fig. 6 Flow changes in Column Flotation

Location of Feed Point

Location of feed point is an important factor since it has a bearing on effectiveness of collection zone. Having a feed point in the lower portion is likely to result in short circuiting of solids to the tailings and also gives less residence time to the solid particles for effective collection. On the other hand having it too close to the interface is likely to disturb it. A compromise is to have the feed point about 2 meter from the top in commercial columns.

Bubble Generators

Bubble generators are termed as the hearts of flotation column. These can be divided into two groups : i) internal and ii) external.

In the early stages of development only internal spargers are used but at present their use is limited to laboratory and pilot test units. The metallurgical performance of these two types of spargers are reported to be similar

Table. 1 Advantages and Disadvantage of Column and Conventional Flotation

S.NO	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES
1.	Less chances of Plugging	Proprietary items and relatively costly
2.	On line maintenance	Operation relatively complicated
3.	Control over bubble size	Need other accessories like pump or high pressure compressor
4.	Long Life	
Internal Spargers		
1.	Relatively Cheap	On line maintenance not possible lead to production loss
2.	Can be fabricated locally	Need to change once in 3 months
3.	Operation is easy	Control of bubble size not possible
4.	Require Low pressure air	

FROTH ZONE

The holdup of air in column froths is around 80%. Increase of J_9 beyond a limit tends to increase hold up in collection zone and reduce the hold up in the froth zone with consequent loss of interface which is not desirable for smooth column operation. In order to reduce the effect of entry of more feed water into the froth zone with increasing J_g more wash water needs to be used. Plant experience indicates that froth depth has no significant effect on metallurgical results

Wash Water

The use of wash water distinguishes the column froth from the conventional cell froth. The purpose of addition of wash water is i) to provide water necessary for the overflow of the collected solids into the launder and ii) to suppress the water coming from the feed from going along with the product in order to prevent the carryover of gangue minerals by entrainment.

3.4 COLUMN FLOTATION vs REVERSE FLOTATION

Let's consider Reverse flotation as conventional flotation. A test was conducted by society for Mining, Metallurgy and Exploration for convention vs column flotation to remove silica. The requirement for higher quality pellets demands that the silica content be lowered to levels ranging from 0.25% – 2.0% SiO_2 . Reverse flotation (silica is floated away from the iron concentrate) has proven to be an economical and effective method for reducing the concentrate silica content to very low levels. Laboratory and commercial test-work has demonstrated some significant metallurgical and economic advantages when column flotation cells are used for this application. Column flotation has become widely accepted throughout the minerals industry. It is no longer considered to be new or risky technology and many new concentrators have incorporated column cells into the Flowsheet. The froth washing system on flotation columns serves two purposes. The first is to provide water for froth stabilization and the second is to displace the process water which normally discharges with the froth.

A number of circuit alternatives were considered:

1. Installation of an additional line of conventional cells
2. Increasing flotation capacity by installing a line of column cells
3. Adding column cells to existing flotation lines to act as recleaners

Fig. 7 Flotation rate decreases as particle size increases

Table. 2 Column Flotation vs Conventional Flotation

Cell Type	% SiO ₂ Concentrate	Flotation Recovery (%)		Total Recovery (%)	
		Weight	%	Weight	%
Conventional	0.9	74.1	91.7	67.7	82.4
Column	0.8	78.2	96.7	71.3	86.4

As the results are favouring column flotation is somehow better than conventional flotation (reverse flotation), to remove silica from the limestone, column flotation can be preferred to conventional one.

CHAPTER 4

PRE-CONCENTRATION

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The strategy of pre-concentration, either by the removal of gangue material before size reduction, or by separation of material for processing by alternate routes, significantly reduces the energy required for comminution, or decreases operating and capital costs. Pre-concentration can be considered as a discrete process step ahead of the main recovery process, aimed at rejecting coarse waste by exploiting the physical properties of the ore. Put simply, it is a process that enriches the ore. This is not a new concept in mineral processing. There is a range of options for pre-concentration, including flotation, screening, optical sorting, x-ray sorting, dense media separation and gravity separation. Each offers its own advantages in terms of throughput, feed size range, capital cost and operating cost. Another similar concept to upgrade or enrich the ore is 'gangue rejection'. Although it is also a process of enriching the ore for downstream treatment, it is effectively removing the gangue or deleterious elements that may affect the downstream process.

The potential to increase feed grades or decrease tonnages to high cost downstream processes has major implications for increasing productivity and decreasing energy costs on a per unit metal basis. It is however always a trade-off between the recovery (or the loss of metal units in the pre-concentration process) versus the operating and capital cost of the process. Pre-concentration can be employed within many flowsheets. The biggest advantage occurs when the process can be performed at a coarse liberation size. The energy required to break the ore and liberate the mineral exponentially increases as it gets finer, so the liberation size of the valuable mineral will dictate the operating cost and the method of pre-concentration that can be employed.

4.2 JIGGING

Jigging is one of the oldest methods of gravity concentration, yet the basic principles are only now beginning to be understood. A mathematical model developed shows considerable promise in predicting jig performance on a size by density basis. The jig is normally used to concentrate relatively coarse material and, if the feed is fairly closed sized

(e.g. 3-10mm), it is not difficult to achieve good separation of a fairly narrow specific gravity range in minerals in the feed (e.g. fluorite, sp. gr. 3.2, from quartz, sp. gr. 2.7).

When the specific gravity difference is large, good concentration is possible with a wider size range. Many large jig circuits are still operated in the coal, cassiterite, tungsten, gold, barytes, and iron-ore industries.

They have a relatively high unit capacity on classified feed and can achieve good recovery of values down to 150 μ m and acceptable recoveries often down to 75 μ m. High proportions of fine sand and slime interfere with performance and the fines content should be controlled to provide optimum bed conditions.

In the jig the separation of minerals of different specific gravity is accomplished in a bed which is rendered fluid by a pulsating current of water so as to produce stratification.

The aim is to dilate the bed of material being treated and to control the dilation so that the heavier, smaller particles penetrate the interstices of the bed and the larger high specific gravity particles fall under a condition probably similar to hindered settling. On the pulsion stroke the bed is normally lifted as a mass, then as the velocity decreases it tends to dilate, the bottom particles falling first until the whole bed is loosened. On the suction stroke it then closes slowly again and this is repeated at every stroke, the frequency usually varying between 55 and 330 c min^{-1} . Fine particles tend to pass through the interstices after the large ones have become immobile. The motion can be obtained either by using a fixed sieve jig, and pulsating the water, or by employing a moving sieve, as in the simple hand-jig.

The initial acceleration of the mineral grains is thus independent of size and dependent only on the densities of the solid and the fluid. Theoretically, if the duration of fall is short enough and the repetition of fall frequent enough, the total distance travelled by the particles will be affected more by the differential initial acceleration, and therefore by density, than by their terminal velocities and therefore by size. In other words, to separate small heavy mineral particles from large light particles a short jiggling cycle is necessary. Although relatively short fast strokes are used to separate fine minerals, more control and better stratification can be achieved by using longer, slower strokes, especially with the coarser particle sizes. It is therefore good practice to screen the feed to jigs into different size ranges and treat these separately.

If the mineral particles are examined after a longer time they will have attained their terminal velocities and will be moving at a rate dependent on their specific gravity and size. Since the bed is really a loosely packed mass with interstitial water providing a very thick suspension of high density, hindered-settling conditions prevail, and the settling ratio of heavy to light minerals is higher than that for free settling. The upward flow can be adjusted so that it overcomes the downward velocity of the fine light particles and carries them away, thus achieving separation. It can be increased further so that only large heavy particles settle, but it is apparent that it will not be possible to separate the small heavy and large light particles of similar terminal velocity. Hindered settling has a marked effect on the separation of coarse minerals, for which longer, slower strokes should be used, although in practice, with coarser feeds, it is improbable that the larger particles have time to reach their terminal velocities. At the end of a pulsion stroke, as the bed begins to compact, the larger particles interlock, allowing the smaller grains to move downwards through the interstices under the influence of gravity.

Fig. 8 Mechanism of Jigging

Fig. 9 Settling of particles

4.3 DENSE MEDIA SEPARATION (DMS)

Dense medium separation (or heavy medium separation (HMS), or the sink-and-float process) is applied to the pre-concentration of minerals, i.e. the rejection of gangue prior to grinding for final liberation. It is also used in coal preparation to produce a commercially graded end-product, clean coal being separated from the heavier shale or high-ash coal. In principle, it is the simplest of all gravity processes and has long been a standard laboratory method for separating minerals of different specific gravity. Heavy liquids of suitable density are used, so that those minerals lighter than the liquid float, while those denser than it sink.

Since most of the liquids used in the laboratory are expensive or toxic, the dense medium used in industrial separations is a thick suspension, or pulp, of some heavy solid in water, which behaves as a heavy liquid. The process offers some advantages over other gravity processes. It has the ability to make sharp separations at any required density, with a high degree of efficiency even in the presence of high percentages of near-density material. The density of separation can be closely controlled, within a relative density of ± 0.005 and can be maintained, under normal conditions, for indefinite periods. The separating density can, however, be changed at will and fairly quickly, to meet varying requirements. The process is, however, rather expensive, mainly due to the ancillary equipment needed to clean the medium and the cost of the medium itself.

Dense medium separation is applicable to any ore in which, after a suitable degree of liberation by crushing, there is enough difference in specific gravity between the particles to separate those which will repay the cost of further treatment from those which will not. The process is most widely applied when the density difference occurs at a coarse particle size, as separation efficiency decreases with size due to the slower rate of settling of the particles. Particles should preferably be larger than about 4 mm in diameter, in which case separation can be effective on a difference in specific gravity of 0.1 or less. Separation down to 500 μm , and less, in size can, however, be made by the use of centrifugal separators. Providing a density difference exists, there is no upper size limit except that determined by the ability of the plant to handle the material. Dense medium separation is possible with ores in which the minerals are coarsely aggregated. If the values are finely disseminated throughout the host rock, then a suitable density difference between the crushed particles cannot be developed by coarse crushing.

Fig. 10 Dense Media Separation

DENSE MEDIUM

LIQUIDS

Heavy liquids have wide use in the laboratory for the appraisal of gravity-separation techniques on ores. Heavy liquid testing may be performed to determine the feasibility of dense medium separation on a particular ore, and to determine the economic separating density, or it may be used to assess the efficiency of an existing dense medium circuit by carrying out tests on the sink and float products. The aim is to separate the ore samples into a series of fractions according to density, establishing the relationship between the high and the low specific gravity minerals.

SUSPENSIONS

Below a concentration of about 15% by volume, finely ground suspensions in water behave essentially as simple Newtonian fluids. Above this concentration, however, the suspension becomes non-Newtonian and a certain minimum stress, or yield stress, has to be applied before shear will occur and the movement of a particle can commence. Thus small particles, or those close to the medium density, are unable to overcome the rigidity offered by the medium before movement can be achieved. This can be overcome to some extent either by increasing the shearing forces on the particles, or by decreasing the apparent viscosity of the suspension. The shearing force may be increased by substituting centrifugal force for gravity. The viscous effect may be decreased by agitating the medium, which causes elements of liquid to be sheared relative to each other. In practice the medium is never static, as motion is imparted to it by paddles, air, etc., and also by the sinking material itself. All these factors, by reducing the yield stress, tend to bring the parting or separating density as close as possible to the density of the medium in the bath.

In order to produce a stable suspension of sufficiently high density, with a reasonably low viscosity, it is necessary to use fine, high specific gravity solid particles, agitation being necessary to maintain the suspension and to lower the apparent viscosity. The solids comprising the medium must be hard, with no tendency to slime, as degradation increases the apparent viscosity by increasing the surface area of the medium. The medium must be easily removed from the mineral surfaces by washing, and must be easily recoverable from the fine-ore particles washed from the surfaces. It must not be affected by the constituents of the ore and must resist chemical attack, such as corrosion.

SEPARATING VESSELS

Several types of separating vessel are in use, and these may be classified into gravitational ("staticbaths") and centrifugal (dynamic) vessels. There is an extensive literature on the performance of these processes, and effective mathematical models are now being developed, which can be used for simulation purposes.

GRAVITATIONAL VESSELS

Gravitational units comprise some form of vessel into which the feed and medium are introduced and the floats are removed by paddles, or merely by overflow. Removal of the sinks is the most difficult part of separator design. The aim is to discharge the sinks particles without removing sufficient of the medium to cause disturbing downward currents in the vessel. The feed is introduced on to the surface of the medium by free-fall, which allows it to plunge several centimetres into the medium. Gentle agitation by rakes mounted on the central shaft helps keep the medium in suspension. The float fraction simply overflows a weir, whilst the sinks are removed by pump or by external or internal air lift.

CHAPTER 5

FLWSHEETS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

The Main objective of the project is to prepare the Flowsheet for the upgradation of Limestone ore.

There are three possible ways:

1. Installation of an additional line of conventional cells
2. Increasing flotation capacity by installing a line of column cells
3. Adding column cells to existing flotation lines to act as re cleaners

By taking these into consideration,

We've created four types of Flowsheets depends upon the percentage of limestone to be upgraded.

1. Beneficiation by Reverse Flotation
2. Beneficiation by Column Flotation
3. Beneficiation by Column Flotation – using Jigging as Pre-concentration
4. Beneficiation by Column Flotation – using DMS as Pre-concentration

5.2 Beneficiation by Reverse Flotation

Here, In this Flowsheet, Reverse Flotation is used as the method of beneficiation to upgrade the Quality of Limestone. The Reverse Flotation is included after grinding. By using this, the silica can be removed effectively in economical manner. But when the silica percentage is too high, the efficiency will come down. So, It can be used in places where less than 7% of silica is there.

5.3 Beneficiation by Column Flotation

Here, In this Flowsheet, Column Flotation is used as the method of beneficiation to upgrade the Quality of Limestone. The Column Flotation is included after grinding. By using this, the silica can be removed effectively in economical manner slightly more than Reverse flotation. It is used to remove up to 14% of silica from Limestone and the cost/tonne is also less.

5.4 Beneficiation by Column Flotation – Using Jigging as Pre-concentration

Here, In this Flowsheet, Column Flotation is used as the method of beneficiation to upgrade the Quality of Limestone along with Jigging as the Pre-concentration. It is included after grinding. After Grinding, the ores will be divided into two grades as high grade and low grade. If the low grade contains more amount of impurities along with silica, pre-concentration may used to separate those impurities. As silica and limestone has more or less same specific gravity, by using pre-concentrators silica and limestone can't be separated but other impurities like $MgCO_3$ can be separated. If the silica is more than 10% and other impurities also there, we can use this to upgrade the quality of limestone.

5.5 Beneficiation by Column Flotation – using DMS as Pre-Concentration

Here, In this Flowsheet, Column Flotation is used as the method of beneficiation to upgrade the Quality of Limestone along with DMS as the Pre-concentration. It is included after grinding. After Grinding, the ores will be divided into two grades as high grade and low grade. If the low grade contains more amount of impurities along with silica, pre-concentration may used to separate those impurities. As silica and limestone has more or less same specific gravity, by using pre-concentrators silica and limestone can't be separated but other impurities like $MgCO_3$ can be separated. If the silica is more than 10% and other impurities also there, we can use this to upgrade the quality of limestone.

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

The upgradation of limestone mainly depends on the Flotation. Here, with the use of column flotation and reverse flotation and combination of both can be used to upgrade the grade of limestone. If the limestone contains any other impurities than silica in a high percentage, then pre-concentration like Jigging or Dense media separation can be used to remove it. The feasibility studies of column and reverse flotation studies shows that, in column flotation the cost/tonne is comparatively less to conventional flotation system.

Hence, the suggestion is Cell and Column Flotation can be installed in Mineral Processing after positive result from the pilot plant test. If the silica level is less than 7% means, the Reverse Flotation as well as Cell and Column Flotation can be used. If the silica level is more than 7%, Cell and Column Flotation can be preferred more than Reverse Flotation. If the silica level is more than 7% and also it contains other impurities, Pre-Concentration method can be used along with cell and column flotation.

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